

IN-FIELD PERFORMANCE OF TRACTOR DRAWN "DIRECT SEEDER OF RICE"

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MS Received: 18.05.2024; MS Revised: 15.06.2024; MS Accepted: 16.06.2024

MS 3213

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURAL PROCESS ENGINEERING,,)

Abstract

Paddy seed sowing is one of the most important operations in paddy cultivation. In Eastern Vidarbha region, paddy sowing and transplanting operation mainly has done by broadcasting and manual transplanting, which is very time and labour consuming and required more seed. Labour scarcity is the main problem in sowing and transplanting period, delay in cultivation and results lowering in the yield of paddy. So, there was a need of replace broadcasting method to direct seeders of rice for perform sowing operation more effectively and on timely. Keeping the view of direct seeders of rice on farm testing conducted on carried out on farmer's field. The average speed of operation was 2.89 km/h and the effective field capacity and field efficiency was found to be 0.40 ha/h and 73.74 % respectively. The yield of paddy was observed 28.35 q/ha respectively.

Keywords: Paddy sowing, forward speed, seed rate and yield

Introduction

In India and the World, Paddy (*Oryza sativa*) is the world's most important crop and a primary food source for more than one third of the population. About 90% of the world's paddy (146.7 million ha of area with a production of 673.6 million tonnes of paddy) is grown and produced in Asia. In Maharashtra paddy is mainly cultivated in Konkan region and eastern region of Vidarbha. There is no high productivity area in Maharashtra. Five districts are under medium productivity group (yield 2,000-2,500 kg/ha) i.e., Sangali, Sindhudurg, Kolhapur, Raigad and Ratnagiri. Eastern Vidarbha districts are lie under the low productivity districts in paddy production (1,000-1,500 Kg/ha). (State wise rice productivity analysis. (Anonymous, 2020).

In Eastern Vidarbha districts namely Gadchiroli, Bhandara, Gondia, Chandrapur and some region of Nagpur paddy is cultivated. Area under paddy cultivation in Gadchiroli District is 1,83,00 ha and mostly broadcasting and manual transplanting method used. In broadcasting method the seed broadcast by hand. This method is practiced in those areas which are comparatively dry and less fertile and do not have much labour work in the fields but very less yield and problem for intercultural operation and in manual transplanting of paddy has a very high demand of manual labour of 360 man-h/ha. The variability of labour availability during peak season of transplanting, creating uncertainty and delays in transplanting results in to lower yields. Also, the delayed transplanting causes a reduced time interval between harvesting and sowing of next crop. (Sharma et al., 2003).

Transplanting of paddy seeding in India is mostly done by manual labour on wages basis. Due to shortage of labour, manual transplanting is becoming difficult. Even in traditional manual transplanting paddy areas like Punjab and Haryana, search for alternate methods started, leading to adoption of direct seeding. Direct seeding of paddy has been in practice in different parts of the

country. Introduction of machine in direct seeding was attempted. Manually operated drum seeders with separate cylindrical seed boxes to drill the pre-germinated paddy seed on puddled soil also gained momentum for some time to overcome the transplanting drudgery. But the main concern with drum seeders was less capacity and suitable only for small scale farming community. Moreover, this method requires considerably higher seed rate and often exposes the seed to damage by birds and environment.

Therefore, it has become imperative to identify alternative methods of paddy cultivation to address the above problems. The direct seeding of paddy technique offers viable option to reduce the limitations of transplanted paddy (Gill, 2014). Dry-seeded paddy (DSR) was a common practice before green revolution in India, is becoming popular once again because of its potential to save water and labour (Gupta et al., 2006). Direct seeded paddy removes puddling, drudgery of transplanting and saving of water. The success of DSR mainly attributed to timely sowing, reduced cost of cultivation, seed rate, fertilizer, water and equal or higher yield as compared to transplanting (Mahajan et al., 2005). Keeping the view of direct seeder of rice on farm testing conduct on assessment was carried out farmer field at Chamorshi and Armori block.

Materials And Methods

Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Sonapur- Gadchiroli conducted on farm testing on 15 farmer fields each year during kharif 2020-2022 to study the economic feasibility of direct seeders of rice. The soil of the experimental site was sandy loam. The experiment consisted of evaluation of field performance of the DSR in comparison with manual broadcasting. The commercial tractor operated multi crop DSR with 11 tyne planter was used for conducting on farm testing. The study was conducted at Dotkuli Tal. Chamorshi and Koregaon Tal. Armori, Dist. Gadchiroli, (MS) in 2020-2022 and the evaluation conducted the variety of paddy PKV- HMT and farmer variety was local (Shriram) are detail are below

Sr. No.	Particulars	Specification
1	Model name	Multi crop rice grain planter
2	Brand	National
3	No. of tyne	Eleven
4	No. of rows	Eleven
5	No. of depth wheel	Two
6	Capacity with seed and fertilizer, (kg)	45 and 44
7	Ground drive wheel type	Lugged

Experimental Procedure

The tractor speed was obtained by recording the time required for the DSR to travel a 20 m distance in the field. Theoretical field capacity and actual field capacity were calculated based on the theoretical area and actual area covered per unit time respectively. Field efficiency

was obtained by dividing actual field capacity by the theoretical field capacity. During the evaluation the forward speed, actual field capacity, field efficiency, seed required, fuel consumption and cost of operation were measure as per standard methods.

1) In field performance of direct seeders of paddy planter

1) Field view of direct seeders of paddy planter

Results And Discussion

The on farm testing on direct seeders of paddy was conducted on 13 farmer's field. Based on the field testing it was observed that the depth of seed sowing is about 2.5-3.2 cm with row to row spacing of 20 cm. The actual average field capacity of the direct seeders of rice was 0.40 ha/h with a field efficiency of 73.54% at an average

operating speed of 2.89 km/h (Table 3). It took 2.5 h to drilling 1 ha area and the fuel consumption was 8.93 l/ha and 3.57 lit/h. The details of field performance results are observed in Table 2.

The working performance of the direct seeders of paddy was found to be satisfactory. It is useful in saving cost, time and energy with increase in the yield.

Table 2. Field performance of direct seeders of rice

Sr. No.	Parameters	Kharif 2020	Kharif 2021	Kharif 2022	Average
1	Date of sowing	15.06.2020	22.06.21	18.06.22	
2	Variety	PKV HMT	PKV HMT	PKV HMT	-
3	Speed of operation, km/h	2.90	2.82	2.95	2.89
4	Time taken to cover 1 ha area, h	2.5	2.55	2.45	2.5
5	Average seed depth, cm	2.5	2.7	3	2.73
6	Average seed spacing, cm	20	20	20	20
7	Seed rate, kg/ha	40.50	38.00	42.30	40.27
8	Actual field capacity, ha/h	0.40	0.39	0.40	0.4

9	Field efficiency, %	72.56	76.40	71.65	73.54
10	Fuel consumption, l/hr	3.50	3.75	3.46	3.57
11	Fuel consumption, l/ha	8.75	9.56	8.48	8.93
12	Cost of economics Rs./ha	1450	1600	1600	1550

Table 3. Comparison between DSR and Broadcasting

Sr. No.	Particulars	DSR	Broadcasting	DSR	Broadcasting	DSR	Broadcasting	DSR	Broadcasting
	Year	2020		2021		2022		Average	
	Paddy	PKV HMT	Local						
1	Grain yield, q/ha	28.40	21.31	27.5	20.05	29.15	19.37	28.35	20.24

Conclusions

In paddy sowing it was observed that the average forward speed of direct paddy seeders was observed at 2.89 km/h and the average field capacity, field efficiency and fuel consumption of the direct paddy seeders was 0.40 ha/h 73.74% and 8.83 l/ha, respectively.

In paddy sowing, it was observed that the average forward speed of direct paddy seeders seed rate per ha was found 40.27 kg and yield of paddy was 28.35 qtl/ha.

The average paddy sowing cost of operation was found to 1550 Rs/ha.

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